

SERVICE LEVEL OBJECTIVES: WHAT'S WORKING AND WHAT'S NOT?

OCTOBER 2020

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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The constant evolution of the IT technologies brings the possibility of providing new services, which also contributes to the increased expectations regarding their functionality and reliability. This results in a constant race of delivering new features whilst aiming to keep the services as reliable as possible and triggers one fundamental question: “How do we know that our service is still good enough in the client’s eyes?”

This is where the Service Level Objectives (SLO) come in place and help to identify the quality of the provided service. Their usage is standard practice in many organisations to monitor, improve the operations, and to establish better communication with the users. SLOs are set on top of measured Service Level Indicators (SLIs) and represent the required per cent of the time that a given SLI should meet the expected quality standards.

The major goal of this project is to study these practices and implement a central SLO dashboard for the IT Monitoring Service at CERN. It will provide SLI/SLO information in near real-time and notify in case of a drop in the service reliability.

ABSTRACT

With the increased complexity of the provided IT services a more sophisticated monitoring approach is required to guaranty their normal operations and reliability. We need to monitor our services from the perspective of the user experience and not only looking after a specific host or operating system parameters. Our website might be up and running but, if it responds slowly, the users will maybe never try to open it again. This problem could be solved easily by implementing the latest Service Level Objective (SLO) monitoring practices that are inspired by the Service Reliability Engineering (SRE) discipline.

This project covers the work required for studying and implementing SLI/SLO dashboard for the need of the IT Monitoring Service at CERN. It describes the main concept and identifies appropriate SLI metrics for monitoring main service parameters. As next steps, it implements a mechanism for gathering the required metrics and calculating SLI and error budget results.

All the information is made available on a single dashboard that provides immediate feedback to the service manager about the short and long-term reliability status on the provided service. In addition, a set of alerts is configured to notify in case of a sudden drop in the service reliability, in order to improve the awareness and decrease the reaction time in case of incidents.

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1. Introduction

The Internet has gone through several changes in the last few years, and it is also changing the interaction between humans and computers, now users are thinking more about software than hardware. The cloud computing can deliver access to complete and complex applications as web services, being equally possible to offer all the infrastructure for a project deployment as a web service [1].

One way to turn the management of large cloud infrastructures easy is the implementation of tools from reliability engineering. Reliability engineering is a field that provides theoretical and practical tools to verify if a system or a product is delivering results without failures for desired periods in specific environments [2]. Recently the concept of Site Reliability Engineering (SRE) was established, it brings a set of tools to monitor the reliability of web-based services; applying the concepts of SRE, it is possible to measure the reliability of a web-based service in metrics such as latency and availability [3]. The metrics provided by SRE tools smartly helps in failures detection, making the service maintenance more efficient.

This report presents a real implementation of SRE in a complex web service system. The CERN IT Monitoring Service (MonIT) provides the monitoring of the CERN data centre and the WLCG collaborations as a web service, making use of some cloud-based services such as ActiveMQ, Kafka, Elasticsearch, Grafana and Kibana [4]. Intending to improve the maintenance of MonIT, SRE tools were used to measure the system reliability regarding the data access and also regarding all the data treatment from the collection until the data presentation layer. As a result, it is possible to have a set of metrics that can show details about the operational status of different parts of the system.

This report is divided into different sections: in the background section some concepts of SRE will be introduced and also some tools used in the project implementation; the system design section goes through details about how the SRE concepts will be applied into MonIT; the implementation section will describe how the SRE metrics are being measured; the results sections will present graphs dashboards with the metrics collected from MonIT.

2. Background

This section will introduce some concepts of Site Reliability Engineering that are the bases for this project implementation, some of the tools used in the development of this project will also be discussed to bring a better understanding of the project.

a. Site Reliability Engineering

According to [5], Site Reliability Engineering can be defined as the incorporation of software engineering aspects into the infrastructure operation to provide a service with high availability. The SRE also concerns a variety of techniques and tools that make possible the measurement of the reliability of a service providing precise information about different aspects of that service and how each part of the service can affect its user experience [3].

Among the SRE concepts, there are three that can be considered the most important for this project, which are, the Service Level Indicator, the Service Level Objective, and the Error Budget.

The Service Level Indicator (SLI) is a metric that measures how a service is performing, for example, a good SLI for a webpage can be the percentage of requests successfully responded in a certain period, an SLI can also be a latency, a throughput, percentage of jobs run on time, and many others [6]. The SLI is a percentage value and can be normally computed by the formula, $SLI = (\sum \text{Good Events} / \sum \text{Events}) * 100$ [3].

The Service Level Objective (SLO) is a target that can be defined to an SLI, the SLO represents the value that the SLI should be above to provide a good user experience. SLOs usually are higher than 90% [6].

The Error Budget (EB) is a metric that establishes a budget for failures in a service. Once the SLO is defined it is possible to assume that every SLI value bellows the SLO represents errors in the system, then the EB defines how much errors can be acceptable in a certain period (usually three months). For example, if it is defined that an SLI can be below its SLO for 20 minutes in a month and after two weeks this SLI has an EB of 5 minutes, represents that the service is requiring for attention [7].

b. Used Tools

Some tools used during the development and implementation of this project have an essential meaning for the project understanding, so that they will be briefly introduced in this subsection.

1. Kubernetes is a cluster platform that automates the management of containers in a Linux environment [8]. All the deployment of a container can be done automatically with Kubernetes, and it will be used to run the scripts responsables for the SLIs measurements.
2. InfluxDB is shameless time-series database (TSDB); this type of database is optimized for measurements that change over the time; all data inside those databases are organized according to its timestamps [9]. All data produced within the scope of this project will be stored in an InfluxDB database; the InfluxDB will also be used to perform some data manipulations.
3. Grafana is an open-source platform that provides a variety of tools for the visualization and analyses of time-series data [10]. Grafana is one of the services that will be monitored with the implementation of this project, and it will also be used to visualize the SRE metrics into graphs.
4. Kibana is another data visualization platform but focused on data storage into Elasticsearch [11]. Kibana provides different options for data visualization and is one of the services monitored by this project.

3. System Design

This section will describe how the SRE concepts will be applied in CERN's monitoring system. In order to get more efficient SLIs, the mentoring system will be divided into two parts: Data Access, where some SLIs will be used to measure the reliability of the components that provide information to the users and Data Pipeline, where the SLIs will be implemented to measure how the data is being processed from the data collection until the storage.

a. Data Access

To check if the system is well delivering the data requested by the users, it is essential to ensure that all HTTP requests for the data providers, Grafana and Kibana, are being answered and that the system is replying within an acceptable delay. To measure these metrics, two SLIs will be used: HTTP Success Rate and HTTP Response Latency.

HTTP Success Rate SLI: measures the availability of the system. To check if the services are available, ten simultaneous requests should be made to Grafana and Kibana to verify the percentage of successful requests. This SLI is computed following the formula, $\text{Success Rate} = (\sum \text{Successful requests} / \sum \text{Requests}) * 100$.

Figure 1. Success Rate SLI

HTTP Response Latency SLI: measures the delay between the HTTP request and the HTTP answer. To verify this delay in a realistic way, ten simultaneous requests are made to the services (Grafana and Kibana), then it is possible to compute the mean delay of these requests. To provide a good user experience, the latency should be below 5 seconds, so the SLI is the percentage of time that the latency is below 5 seconds in a certain period. This SLI is computed following the formula, $\text{Response Latency} = (\text{Number of responses} < 5 \text{ seconds} / \text{Total number of requests}) * 100$.

Figure 2. Response Latency SLI

b. Data Pipeline

To measure the reliability through all the data pipeline inside the monitoring system, two crucial points should be analysed: if all data sent to the system is available for the users and how much time does it take to process that data. Two SLIs will be used for this purpose: Completeness and Freshness.

To make these measurements possible, it is important to inject some controlled data into the system, so 100 logs documents and 250 metrics documents should be created and sent to the monitoring system before every SLI measurement. This is required in order to guaranty the constant flow of data into the pipeline as many of the data sources are controlled by the clients of the service.

Completeness: measures the percentage of well-processed documents. After the generation of the controlled test data, a request should be made to the system in order to count the number of available documents; then it will be possible to analyse if all the injected data are available for the users. This SLI is computed following the formula, $\text{Completeness} = (\sum \text{Available Documents} / \sum \text{Generated Documents}) * 100$.

Figure 3. Completeness SLI

Freshness: measures how fresh is the data available in the monitoring system. The first step to compute this SLI is to request different data available inside the system and compare the data timestamp with the actual time ($\Delta = \text{actual time} - \text{data timestamp}$), then it is possible to analyse the percentage of data above the threshold (60 seconds). This SLI is computed following the formula, $\text{Freshness} = (\text{Number of } \Delta < 60\text{s} / \text{Total number of } \Delta) * 100$.

Figure 4. Freshness SLI

4. Implementation

To compute the metrics (SLIs) described in section 3, Python scripts are running in a Kubernetes cluster. These scripts can make periodic data requests and uploads to the system in a controlled manner, thus being able to analyse the reliability of the system through different metrics. All the metrics computed by these scripts are stored in a time-series database (InfluxDB); calculations are performed at the database level in order to convert the gathered metrics into proper SLIs.

a. Data Access

In order to monitor the reliability of the resources (Grafana and Kibana) a script was developed to check if the monitored service is available and how long it takes to respond. As described in Figure 5, the script makes simultaneous requests to a resource to observe its reaction in stressful situations.

Figure 5. Data Access Script

The main function of the script verifies which resource should be checked and its URL. Therefore, a function called Check Metrics (Figure 6) verifies the availability of the service, so that the data can be organized and sent to the monitoring system.

Using the aiohttp and asyncio Python libraries, multiple HTTP requests (10 requests) are sent in parallel to the corresponding resource in the function Check Metrics. After receiving the response, two metrics are analysed: the success rate and the response delay. The success rate is the number of successful HTTP requests (code 200) divided by the total number of requests, and the response delay is a simple mean of each request delay.

Figure 6. Check Metrics function

Once computed, these metrics are organized into documents and sent to the monitoring system.

b. Metrics and Logs Generation

The first step to measure SLIs to analyse the whole data pipeline in the monitoring system is the generation of a controlled set of random data to be injected into the system. The script described in Figure 7 is responsible for the generation of random, metrics and logs, test data.

Figure 7. Test data generator script

The metrics documents are composed by a set of randomly generated fields from different data types in order to cover wider data range.

Depending on the configuration, the script generates the random metrics or logs data, and organises it into documents. Thus, the documents are combined and sent to the monitoring system.

c. Completeness

This script is the base for the computation of completeness SLI. As described in Figure 8, the script requests the test data from Grafana or Kibana, check the number of available documents and send this information

to the monitoring system. These data will be used later in the database to be compared with the number of generated documents.

Figure 8. Completeness counter script

d. Freshness

The script described in Figure 9 was developed to compute the metrics required for the Freshness SLI. This script requests the most recent available data for the generated documents (metrics and logs) and also for other data available in the monitoring system. The script then compares the documents' timestamps with the actual time, computing the difference (Δ) between those times. The result is the base for the freshness SLI and once computed it is sent to the monitoring system.

Figure 9. Freshness computer script

e. InfluxDB Continuous Queries

An InfluxDB continuous query (CQ) is a query that runs automatically and periodically on the new data stored in the database. It could be used for applying mathematical operations on top of the received data, and in that case, it allows to complete the SLIs computation process. There are two sets of CQs used to compute the final results that are applied at two steps. First SLIs are calculated from raw metrics and after the Error Budget metrics are calculated by using the already computed SLI results. All applied calculations for each of the metric types will be described in more detail in the next lines:

· Completeness

The completeness script sends to the database the number of correctly stored generated test documents received by the monitoring system. To compute the completeness SLI in percentage, a CQ is used to compare the acquired number with the expected result. This calculation is done by a simple rule of three, i.e. if the expected number of correctly stored generated documents is 250, the CQ calculates: $SLI (\%) = (\Sigma \text{ Available Documents} / 250) * 100$

· Freshness

Calculating any latency SLIs requires an extra step as latency thresholds drive them. In that case, the acceptable latency was defined as 60 seconds, meaning that each flow reported by the freshness script to have data older than that threshold will be reported as unreliable at 0%. As the measurements are gathered every minute, aggregations over more extended periods (5 ~ 10 minutes) are provided for better assessing the situation and minimising the impact of single intervals with slightly increased latency. Thus, the SLI is computed by the percentage of latencies values smaller than the threshold.

· Access

The access latency is computed similarly to the freshness one but with the only difference that the threshold for access was set to 5 seconds. The other access SLI (HTTP response success) is already received in prepared format from the script, and simple CQ is applied only to convert it into a percentage.

· Error Budgets

The second set of CQs, responsible for calculating the error budgets for the different categories, share the same logic, and will be described together. They are applied on the SLIs as moving average over 14 days period, and their SLOs are subtracted from that result. The final numbers are scaled into a 0-100% interval.

5. Results

Once implemented, all resulting data from SRE analyses can be visualized directly in the database (InfluxDB) or using different data visualization tools; in this project, all metrics are displayed in a Grafana dashboard. This section will present the resulting dashboard with the metrics collected from the monitoring system.

a. Dashboard

The dashboard is divided into five parts: the main view, that presents the actual values of each SLI; the Completeness and Freshness parts, that provides information about all the data pipeline; the Access part, that shows the SLIs related with the data acquisition into the monitoring system and the Detailed Metrics part, that have plots of all produced data by the scripts in raw metrics format.

The main view part (Figure 10) shows the actual value of each SLI and the error budgets for a selected period. This information can show if there is an ongoing outage on the system and where possible failures can be found. At the moment showed in Figure 10, the system is working correctly, but some delays may have occurred in the past few days, as the error budget panel for Data Freshness is indicating.

Figure 10. Dashboard header

The first part above the main view is the Completeness part, as it is possible to see in Figure 11, this part shows the current values as in the main view, the completeness SLI for logs and metrics documents, and error budgets also divided into logs and metrics. In this situation, 100 logs and 250 metrics documents are being injected into the data pipeline per minute, in most of the time 100% of the injected data is available, and there are some points where the documents were not delivered correctly due to instability of the environment where the document generation scripts are working.

Figure 11. Completeness section

Figure 12 shows the Freshness part of the dashboard. All the dashboard parts have a similar layout. Thus, it is possible to see the current values for the SLIs and error budgets for logs, metrics, and Collectd documents. The freshness SLI is around 100% at most of the time, but sometimes it has small reductions, indicating slight delays in the data delivery.

Figure 12. Freshness section

The Access part can be divided into two subparts: success rate (Figure 13) and latency (Figure 14). Following the same layout, the actual values, SLIs, and error budgets per resource are displayed. For both Grafana and Kibana, the data can be successfully accessed by the user in almost 100% of the cases.

Figure 13. Response success rate section

For the latency subpart, a layout similar to the Freshness part is implemented. It is possible to find the actual values and the complete graphs per resource. The system responds typically in the expected time (100%) with some points of unavailability.

Figure 14. Response latency section

b. Alerts

It is possible to define alerts in Grafana, so the errors in the system can be easily detected. Some alerts were implemented for the SLIs and error budgets in order to notify the service managers in case of outage and drops of the reliability. The created alarms are triggered when the values go below the following thresholds:

- Errors budgets are below 30%
- Completeness is below 80%
- Data access rate is below 80%
- Latencies are below 70%

6. Future Works

This project has provided a fully implemented SRE solution for the IT Monitoring Service at CERN, but it would also be considered as fundamental for the future evolution of that work. The SRE is considered as ever-evolving monitoring process as the SLOs require to be adjusted once having a more representative set of data, and new SLIs might be required to cover new features and functionality provided by the service to the end-users.

The metrics and SLIs selected by the current project cover the most common data paths in the MonIT pipeline and provide useful indicators for the overall reliability of the infrastructure; nevertheless, the implementation could be extended to cover additional uncovered producers (JDBC, ActiveMQ) and storage systems (HDFS). There is also room for implementing a completely new set of metrics to measure the throughput of the pipeline and the different components.

7. Conclusion

The increasing demand for web services on the lines of Software as a Service, Infrastructure as a Service, Monitoring as a Service, etc. also increases the demand for more complex cloud structures, that have high maintenance costs. Different tools are being developed to simplify and to automate the deployment and the maintenance of these structures; the SRE provides leading techniques to make failure detection more precise, efficient, and straightforward inside the services.

All SRE concepts, as they were applied in this project, can provide highly precise information about the reliability of the IT Monitoring Service at CERN, it detects possible failures in real-time in any part of the system infrastructure and measures the amount of time the service performs below the expectations.

The SRE techniques used in this project are reducing the maintenance time as it can expose the source of the problems, and also make it possible for errors to be detected before they become noticeable by the clients and end-users. These techniques, as they were implemented, are generic and can be useful in many different services, either being a web or any other type of systems.

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